

Open schooling: Collaboration between schools and society to promote students' relevant and meaningful biology learning

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Theoretical background or rationale

Modern societies face a wide range of complex challenges, such as fighting climate change, protecting the environment, and promoting healthy living. To successfully address such challenges, citizens must actively engage in public dialogue and participate responsibly in science-informed decision making. Conventional schooling has not been able to achieve this goal: There is a wide-spread lack of scientific knowledge at all level of society and students' interest in science tends to decline within school years (Hazelkorn et al., 2015; Potvin & Hasni, 2014). This is often due to abstract and decontextualized science teaching (Christidou, 2011), negatively impacting also students' feeling of self-efficacy (Barmby et al., 2008). To address this problem and to ensure students' relevant and meaningful biology learning, we need to overcome the gap between school and real life and promote students' engagement with socio-scientific issues fostering interest, empowerment and authentic biology learning.

The European H2020 project MULTIPLIERS aims to expand science learning through *open-schooling*, i.e., fostering cooperation between schools and society and involving the students in real-life projects. To achieve this, the project has established novel learning partnerships ("Open Science Communities") where schools, families, research institutions, industry, informal learning providers, policy makers, and media collaborate in order to foster the students' engagement with contemporary challenges. In these learning projects ("Open School Science learning projects = OSS projects), the students work with various stakeholders to explore different perspectives and improve their understanding while gaining first-hand experiences and insights into research practices and discussions. The students then act as "multipliers", sharing their knowledge through family involvement and community events or by creating science communication media, such as podcasts and videos.

Key objectives

In our presentation, we will focus on three biology education case studies from Germany, Slovenia and Sweden where students and science experts worked together on different socio-scientific issues. Evaluation studies were conducted to identify methodological approaches and learning environments that promote relevant and meaningful biology learning.

Research design and methodology

For the evaluation of the OSS projects, we collected qualitative data from participant observations and semi-structured interviews as well as focus group discussions with the participants (i.e., students, teachers, science experts, families, and community members).

In Germany, two secondary school classes (students' age 13-14 and 16-17 years) participated in an OSS project on *vaccination*. They collaborated with immunobiology researchers, medical students and ethics experts, visiting different lab facilities and engaging in discussions about vaccination programs. During the multipliers phase, the students created an explanatory video and podcasts for peers and student outreach.

In Slovenia, OSS projects on *biodiversity and ecosystem services* included students from two primary school classes (students' age 6-11 years), science experts from research institutions and NGOs, as well as media and outdoor education experts. Students utilized "natural science backpacks" containing everyday items, such as stings, spoons and knives, and technical equipment, such as binoculars and laboratory tubes. They used these backpacks at home, involving their parents in the learning processes for one week to observe and explore various living environments of their choice, and document findings in research diaries. Additional multiplying activities took place at a science fair and through science communication media production.

Swedish students (two classes, 15-17 years) collaborated with science experts from research institutions, forest industry professionals, and media on the topic of *forest use vs. forest protection*. Students engaged in role-play debates and critically analyzed media representations of forest issues. They also conducted interviews with individuals from three different generations about their relationships to forests, thereby involving community members of various ages and cultural backgrounds and discussing values and individual experiences.

Findings

The data show that the engagement in scientific practices using authentic equipment triggered the students' interest. High attention and students' engagement was also observed and reported for the different debate activities. It was found that promoting the students' autonomy and leadership, while taking on the role of knowledge multipliers, fostered their interest, self-efficacy, and knowledge acquisition. Students were particularly positive about out-of-school experiences in authentic settings, opportunities to work independently in groups, and about the support of the experts. The possibility to ask personal questions about the experts' careers as well as gaining insights into their everyday (work)life was mentioned as another highlight in the student interviews.

The experts themselves stated that they value the interaction with the students as well as their critical questions, and the students' interest in the topics and in their work. They also appreciate the collaboration in the project as a good opportunity for science communication.

Our data show that flexibility in timing and a constant communication, as well as clear tasks and role distributions are necessary to enable a successful cooperation between schools, science experts and other societal stakeholders.

Conclusions

Learning partnerships where schools and societal stakeholders work together to enable the students' engagement with socio-scientific issues help to promote relevant and meaningful biology learning, fostering the student's interest and empowerment. In the MULTIPLIERS project, further OSS projects will be conducted and evaluated in order to derive final recommendations and publish guidelines and materials for successful open-schooling activities.

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